

Preliminary diversity study of Odonates on a waterlogged landscape

Odonates has been recognised as bio-indicators that have implications for the state of the environment as a whole. They serve as a crucial instrument for many types of evaluations and monitoring, including the measurement of biodiversity, the health and integrity of wetlands or biological effects of climate change. The purpose of the current study was to examine the diversity of odonates that can be found living in urban areas.

The investigation was conducted in the centre of Thampanoor city in an abandoned, water-logged landscape (8°29'32"N 76°56'57" E). It has a large range

Paragomphus lineatus

of shrub species and only a few tree species, covering an area of roughly 60 to 70 cents. Passiflora species, Calotropis species and Moringa oleifera were a few prominent floras.

Investigation location at Thampanoor city

The current investigation was conducted in September 2021. All of the field trips were conducted in the forenoon when odonate activity was at its peak. Odonates were identified using Visual Encounter Survey (VES) and photographed using a Nikon D5600 DSLR camera with a 70-300mm lens. Species identification was confirmed using taxonomic monographs of Fraser (1933,1934,1936) and field guides (Subramanian 2009; Nair 2011; Kiran & Raju 2013).

Pantala flavescens

short-term study period has encompassed 22 species of odonates spread across 6 families and two suborders. The highest number of odonates recorded belonged to the family Libellulidae (13 species) followed by Coenagrionidae (4 species), Chlorocyphidae (2 species), Aeshnidae, Gomphidae and Lestidae (one species each).

Crocothemis servilia

The most dominant species was *Pantala flavescens* (Fabricius, 1798) which belongs to Libellulidae family. This could be due to the mass emergence of the species after the monsoon and their yearly aggregation before migration to Eastern Africa (Anderson 2009). Some of the other notable odonates which we found out were *Lestes elatus*, *Ischnura senegalensis*, *Pseudagrion rubriceps* and *Paragomphus lineatus*. All of the reported odonate species are staged under the IUCN Red List's Least Concern category, with the exception of *Gynacantha dravida* Lieftinck, 1960, which is categorised as Data Deficient.

Lestes elatus

Only 12% of Kerala's total odonate species are represented in the current list of odonates due

to the search's restricted geographic scope. The study nevertheless emphasises the significance of regional biodiversity documentation. Due to their amphibious life history, relatively short generation time, high trophic position and diversity, order Odonata are considered an important component of freshwater ecosystems as well as good indicators of ecosystem health. This reiterates the fact that more systematic exploration of biodiversity should be carried out in urban landscapes, especially in light of increasing anthropogenic influences and habitat transformations. Major changes in the degradation of the quality of available

habitats of the urban regions could result in the loss of regional odonate diversity. These changes could also have a cascading effect on terrestrial biodiversity. As with the current study, frequent surveys are needed to further understand this connection, and citizen science initiatives should be encouraged.

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